

The BreedingValue integrated data platform

E. Senger¹, P. Shaw², S. Raubach², K. Olbricht³, B. Usadel¹

¹ Forschungszentrum Jülich, Institute of Bio- and Geosciences, IBG-4 Bioinformatics, BioSC, CEPLAS, Jülich, Germany; ² The James Hutton Institute, Department of Information and Computational Sciences, Invergowrie, Scotland, United Kingdom; ³ Hansabred GmbH & Co. KG, Dresden, Germany

Abstract

In the EU-funded project BreedingValue, we are following a holistic approach to generate the necessary data and know-how required to conduct comprehensive breeding programs aimed at developing modern berry cultivars that are both globally competitive and satisfy the demands of a growing market. Not only are we characterizing and storing variation held in plant genetic resources, but also information from pre-breeding material, selection populations, traditional and modern cultivars. The germplasm used in this work is phenotypically characterized in the field and greenhouse and genotypic analyses are performed using molecular markers. A metabolomic study will develop a better understanding of the metabolites underlying environmental stresses and help identify crucial compounds that constitute aroma, flavor and taste characteristics. This will be combined with a sensory study conducted with a trained panel of sensory experts. Finally, consumer preferences across Europe are assessed via an acceptance study and an online survey.

As part of the Open Data initiative of the EU and following FAIR principles (making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), data, metadata and results of BreedingValue will be made publicly available using the online platform Germinate (<https://germinateplatform.github.io/get-germinate>) that serves as data repository for a diverse range of species covering cereals, legumes and solanaceous crops. Not only growers and breeders but also researchers from other disciplines can benefit from the data stored on the platform, share, and re-use it for further purposes. Additionally, data from previous projects as well as published data from other sources will be integrated. Visualization tools will be developed so that users' can interact and explore their data. Machine learning approaches will reveal trait associations that link phenotype, genetical background and metabolomics. Raw data can be made available for download in standard formats.

Here we will present the data management platform.

Keywords: multi-omics data, data management, data repository, berry breeding, FAIR data

INTRODUCTION

Data are produced at an increasing speed and quantity in the today's 'era of big data'. Alongside innovative technologies to collect data, there is a requirement to provide tools to manage, store and analyze data (Lee, 2017). Crucial developments have been made in the area of computing providing increased memory capacity and CPU performance, bioinformatics providing new models, algorithms and methods, and databases providing the framework for standardized documentation as well as a long-term storage environment, amongst others. Furthermore, there is a strong trend towards open science and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable; Wilkinson et al. 2016) data in recent years, i.e. research data is increasingly publicly available and meets requirements for merging datasets.

In bioscience, 'omics' data are increasingly combined to 'multi-omics' approaches to elucidate biological systems, instead of focusing on a single data source (Gomez-Cabrero et al., 2014). Most important 'omics' technologies in bioscience comprise genomics ("the quantitative study of protein coding genes, regulatory elements and noncoding sequences"), transcriptomics (the study of "RNA and gene expression"), proteomics (the study of proteins, "e.g. focusing on protein abundance"), and metabolomics (the study of "metabolites and

metabolic networks”), amongst others (Schneider and Orchard, 2011). Although plant science from a historical point of view was dominated by phenotyping (the observation of gene expressions, i.e. includes but is not limited to metabolomics), plant researchers and breeders nowadays combine these technologies to elucidate the genetic background of phenotypic observations, unravel unknown associations between the different parameters across ‘omics’, amongst others (Bolger et al., 2019). This supports the development of genotyping tools to reduce the resource-intensive phenotyping efforts dedicated to identification of desired phenotypes and understanding of complex biological mechanisms such as plants’ resilience to biotic and abiotic stress factors, causing agents of sensory attributes, or similar (Varshney et al., 2021).

Numerous online databases have evolved as public repositories for large omics datasets. Examples of established, long-term curated platforms for omics related to plant sciences are the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) for sequencing data, the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) for biomedical and genomic information, the Proteomics Identification Database (PRIDE) for protein and peptide identification, or the MetaboLights database for metabolomic data, amongst others. Major drawbacks of most databases are limited number of represented omics disciplines and challenging information extraction for non-expert users. In particular for agricultural or plant science, the lack of phenotyping data and association between the different omics data has motivated the creation of the platform ‘Germinate’ (<https://germinateplatform.github.io/get-germinate>). Its basic idea is to share holistic information about genetic resources to combat loss of genetic diversity in established crops and to diversify the existing panel of cultivated plants (Shaw et al., 2017; Raubach et al., 2020). On one hand it is addressing researchers and breeders, and at the other hand it appeals untrained persons such as students, politicians, journalist, and others to access, browse and visualize information in the user-friendly interface and use the interactive tools. Furthermore, the platform fulfills a common requirement of journals and funding agencies that data be made publicly available and support standard digital formats which can be easily utilized by others (Shaw et al., 2017). This is also important in ensuring germplasm and variation generated in projects such as BreedingValue are exploited within the research and breeding communities. To safeguard good scientific practice and guarantee a long-term impact of any research data, guidelines have been established through initiatives such as FAIR, where research data should meet the principles of being findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016) in order to help data uptake and utilization. Such guidelines ensure that data can be easily found, used and distributed in standard, plain-text, file formats.

Germinate hosts data of 22 crops such as cereals, legumes and solanaceous crops. The platform links germplasm information, phenotyping as well as genotyping data, environmental data and metadata (Figure 1), which are fully compliant with the Minimal Information About a Plant Phenotyping Experiment (MIAPPE) (Ćwiek-Kupczyńska et al., 2016; Papoutsoglou et al., 2020) and the Multi-Crop Passport Descriptors (MCPD V.2.1) introduced by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (Alercia et al., 2015). The platform provides the infrastructure and tools to store, explore, interact and understand large and complex datasets. Apart from browsing and filtering in the single datasets, it provides tools for visualization of e.g. origin of collected germplasm accessions on a global map, galleries of exemplary photographs of phenotypic observations, molecular marker maps, as well as statistical overviews of groups that have been indexed in the datasets (Shaw et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Overview of datasets that can be integrated to Germinate.

The project BreedingValue, funded by European Union under the Horizon2020 program, aims providing promising pre-breeding material as well as innovative tools to the breeding and research community with a focus on strawberry, raspberry and blueberry in Europe (Senger et al., 2022). The project consortium consists of 20 research partners and breeders from eight European countries. More than 2200 germplasm accessions and 33 breeding populations will be provided by the project consortium and further accessions by participants of open calls. The first project period started with phenotypic and genotypic characterization of the material to define a core collection and assess the current status of European breeding programs. At the same time, consumer science targets identification of requirements and trends on the market. Historic and publicly available data will complement the project data. To achieve the ambitious goals and catch up leeway of berry breeding in Europe, a holistic multi-omics approach has been set up based on a very large germplasm collection and the combination of the numerous disciplines (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Organization and outputs of the BreedingValue project (© BreedingValue consortium, 2022).

THE BREEDINGVALUE APPROACH

The germplasm collection consists of crucial accessions contributed by the consortium members and is divided into several categories to distinguish old from modern cultivars, newest releases from current breeding programs, selfing lines, populations and few wild species accessions representing the species background of the cultivated forms (Senger et al., 2022). The accessions are grown in trials in the open field, protected field and greenhouse. Some accessions to be included exclusively in genotyping studies will be sampled from germplasm maintenance plots. The trials serve for phenotyping in the important European berry growing areas across two seasons. Descriptor traits defined as standards in previous EU berry projects will include yield, physiological characteristics and fruit quality attributes including determination of metabolites and volatiles in ripe fruits. The latter is combined with degustation of fruits by a trained panel in order to identify substances that constitute specific taste and aroma sensations. A comprehensive understanding will be developed on how the different accessions response to environmental conditions by multi-factorial statistical analysis. Furthermore, breeding progress in defined traits can be shown when comparing the phenotypic data of the different germplasm categories. Specific breeding goals will be addressed in smaller subsets, such as drought tolerance and resistances to diseases of commercial importance.

Three genomic approaches will be followed, starting with characterizing the projects' germplasm collection and further accessions provided by breeders using molecular markers that are known to be associated to commercially important monogenic traits and major quantitative trait loci (QTL) that are stable across different environments. Existing marker arrays available for strawberry and raspberry will be advanced, and a potential marker array for blueberry might be developed for modernization of marker-assisted selection (MAS) in the three berry species. In a second approach, genome-wide association studies (GWAS) and genomic prediction models will be designed as tools for targeting traits with complex inheritance. The results of both approaches will be validated with participants of open calls, which also serves for training and technology transfer to breeders that are not members of the project consortium. In the third approach, an allelic diversity study will be performed on the projects' germplasm collection and further accessions provided by breeders through open

calls to assess the genetic diversity present in the different germplasm categories. It will help to identify crucial genetic resources to be transferred to breeders for future breeding, to determine breeding progress or breeding regress over the last decades in target traits, and to spot the potentials and deficits of current breeding programs.

In the area of consumer science, the project will analyze data obtained through an online survey that aims determining consumer preferences with regard to fruit quality traits, sensory attributes, cultivation methods and pricing. The survey was translated to eight languages, including Chinese, to motivate a high number of participants. Information on participant age, gender, economic status and similar will enable grouping of the dataset and find group-specific preferences.

The data of the numerous disciplines generated during the project will be made publicly available in Germinate alongside relevant published data from other sources. Germplasm information, genotypic data, phenotypic data, metabolite profiles and environmental data will be present in separate menus and can be visualized within and across menus. Analytical tools will be provided so that users can work with the datasets directly online to find e.g. associations between datasets or identify patterns in the data. Germinate needs to be extended by a section to visualize data of the consumer preferences obtained through the online survey. A challenge will be to link it to the other datasets that are accession-based.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The BreedingValue project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101000747.

Literature cited

- Alercia, A., Diulgheroff, S., and Mackay, M. (2015). FAO/Biodiversity Multi-Crop Passport Descriptors V.2.1. (MCPD V.2.1), FAO Rome, Italy; Biodiversity International, Rome, Italy, pp. 11.
- Bolger, A.M., Poorter, H., Dumschott, K., Bolger, M.E., Arend, D., Osorio, S., Gundlach, H., Mayer, K.F., Lange, M., Scholz, U., and Usadel, B. (2019). Computational aspects underlying genome to phenome analysis in plants. *Plant J.* 97 (1), 182–198.
- Ćwiek-Kupczyńska, H., Altmann, T., Arend, D., Arnaud, E., Chen, D., Cornut, G., Fiorani, F., Frohberg, W., Junker, A., Klukas, C., et al. (2016). Measures for interoperability of phenotypic data: minimum information requirements and formatting. *Plant Methods* 12, 44.
- Gomez-Cabrero, D., Abugessaisa, I., Maier, D., Teschendorff, A., Merckenschlager, M., Gisel, A., Ballestar, E., Bongcam-Rudloff, E., Conesa, A., and Tegnér, J. (2014). Data integration in the era of omics: current and future challenges. *BMC Syst Biol.* 8 Suppl 2, I1. doi: 10.1186/1752-0509-8-S2-I1. Epub 2014 Mar 13.
- Lee, I. (2017). Big data: dimensions, evolution, impacts, and challenges. *Bus. Horiz.* 60 (3), 293–303.
- Papoutsoglou, E.A., Faria, D., Arend, D., Arnaud, E., Athanasiadis, I.N., Chaves, I., Coppens, F., Cornut, G., Costa, B.V., Ćwiek-Kupczyńska, H., et al. (2020). Enabling reusability of plant phenomic datasets with MIAPPE 1.1. *New Phytol.* 227, 260–273.
- Raubach, S., Kilian, B., Dreher, K., Amri, A., Bassi, F.M., Boukar, O., Cook, D., Cruickshank, A., Fatokun, C., Had dad, N.E., et al. (2021). From bits to bites: advancement of the Germinate platform to support prebreeding informatics for crop wild relatives. *Crop Sci.* 61, 1538–1566.
- Schneider, M.V., and Orchard, S. (2011). Omics Technologies, Data and Bioinformatics Principles. In *Bioinformatics for Omics Data*, Mayer, B., ed. (Methods in Molecular Biology vol. 719, Humana Press), p. 3–30.
- Senger, E., Osorio, S., Olbricht, K., Shaw, P., Denoyes, B., Davik, J., Predieri, S., Karhu, S., Raubach, S., Lippi, N., et al. (2022). Towards smart and sustainable development of modern berry cultivars in Europe. *Plant J.* 2022 Jun 24. doi: 10.1111/tbj.15876. Epub ahead of print.

- Shaw, P., Raubach, S., Hearne, S.J., Dreher, K., Bryan, G., McKenzie, G., Milne, I., Stephen, G., and Marshall, D.F. (2017). Germinate 3: Development of a common platform to support the distribution of experimental data on crop wild relatives. *Crop Sci.* 57 (3), 1259–1273.
- Varshney, R.K., Bohra, A., Yu, J., Graner, A., Zhang, Q., and Sorrells, M.E. (2021). Designing future crops: genomics-assisted breeding comes of age. *Trends Plant Sci.* 26 (6), 631–649.
- Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E., et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3, 160018.